

A Comparative Study of the Morpho-Syntactic and Lexical Features of African American
Vernacular English in East Coast vs. West Coast Style Rap

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Abstract

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This dissertation studies African American Vernacular English (AAVE, henceforth) found in the East Coast style rap (ECSR, henceforth) and the West Coast style rap (WCSR, henceforth), which are two varieties of AAVE. This dissertation is aimed at looking for all the sub-features that fall under three major features of AAVE – tense & aspect marking feature, negation feature, and pronoun feature in the two AAVE varieties and compare them. In this way, two databases have been created in this dissertation for the two AAVE varieties – ECSR and WCSR respectively. Both qualitative method and quantitative methods have been applied to this dissertation, in which the qualitative method is used to identify and analyze the data and the descriptive quantitative method is used to calculate the percentage of each feature found in the databases. As for the conclusion, first off, there is a group of sub-features found in both databases that have been built for this dissertation. Take a closer look at the sub-features found in both databases – as for the tense & aspect marking sub-features, there are some sub-features that show up extremely similar amount of times in both databases, i.e. the usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta*, while there are some other sub-features, i.e. *done* + verb (past tense form), differ largely in terms of how many times it has showed up in both databases; in the negation sub-features, both databases have exactly the same sub-features, which are the usage of *ain't*, double negation, and the usage of *don't*, out of which the usage of *ain't* has become the most often used negation sub-feature in both databases; in the pronoun sub-features, there is only one sub-feature that two databases have in common, which is the usage of *y'all*, which has shown up a bit more in the WCSR database than the ECSR database.

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1. Introduction

Much of the linguistic literature has written about the morpho-syntactic and lexical features of African American Vernacular English (AAVE, henceforth). However, few have discussed the morpho-syntactic and lexical features of AAVE through rap music, which is a variety of AAVE. So, to fill in the gap, this dissertation is going to study the morpho-syntactic and lexical features through rap music – to put it more clearly, a comparative study between East Coast style rap (ECSR, henceforth) and West Coast style rap (WCSR, henceforth) would be the focus of this dissertation. However, morpho-syntactic and lexical features of AAVE have a very broad range, which would be difficult to cover and discuss in this dissertation. To narrow down the range, a preliminary data analysis, which can be found in chapter 3, has been conducted to decide which aspect that this dissertation is going to focus on, and it turns out that three major features of AAVE might find the similarities and differences between ECSR and WCSR, which are tense & aspect marking feature, negation feature, and pronoun feature. In this way, the focus of this dissertation has been decided – a comparative study on ECSR and WCSR regarding tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronoun forms of AAVE.

In this dissertation, there are 7 chapters in total - chapter 1 for introduction, chapter 2 for literature review, chapter 3 for methodology, chapter 4 & 5 for data description and analysis, chapter 6 for data comparison, and chapter 7 for conclusion.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Rap Linguistics

There are 5 sections in this literature review chapter – (i) rap linguistics, (ii) general introduction of AAVE, (iii) tense & aspect marking of AAVE, (iv) negation of AAVE, (v) pronouns of AAVE.

In general, there are many linguistic studies that have been done before discussing the tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronouns of AAVE, which can be seen in linguistic works like Dillard (1973), Fickett (1972), Green (2002), Labov (1972), Wolfram (2004), and many more, which will be discussed in the rest of the sections in this chapter. However, when it comes to studying the usage of AAVE in rap lyrics, few studies have been done before.

Linguistic scholar Darin Flynn has been known for rap linguistics (“A New Way Media Interview,” 2006), where he discussed his research interest on rap linguistics, especially on syntax. However, few academic work can be found of him, while there is a list of media articles written by him (“Rap Linguistics,” n.d.), most of which can no longer be found and most of which are for general audience. At the same time, there are other linguistic

studies on rap - Yasin (1998) explores “how language in the lyrics of rap music is mapped onto the musical meter”, Duranti (2009) discusses linguistic anthropology, Alim (2002) investigates “stylistic variation and identity in schools and society from the dual perspectives of quantitative sociolinguistics and linguistic anthropology”, Alim & Ibrahim & Pennycook (2008) talks about the culture, identity, and politics expressed through hip-hop, and Smitherman (1977) explores the sounds and semantics of AAVE. Unfortunately, few of the linguistic works just mentioned focuses on the syntax of AAVE in rap lyrics, not to mention conducting a comparative study discussing the difference of AAVE syntax features between ECSR and WCSR, which is the focus of this dissertation.

2.2 General Introduction of AAVE

According to Green (2002), AAVE, namely African American Vernacular English, is considered as an English variety, which has its own system of phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and lexicon, and it means that users of AAVE is supposed to use it consistently. There are many different theories towards the origin of AAVE, one of which claims that it originates “as a creole such as Jamaican Creole and Gullah, which is spoken in the Sea Islands off the coast of South Carolina and Georgia”, which explains the reason why AAVE shares patterns with “creole varieties of English (e.g., Jamaican Creole and Gullah) and with other dialects of English” (Green, 2002). Different names that have been given to this variety of English – from Negro dialect, to Black dialect, to Black English, to African American English, to African American Vernacular English, and many more, out of which AAVE is one of the most common names for this variety and all of which have referred to the same system of English (Green, 2002). In this dissertation, the name African American Vernacular English is used to refer to this system of English dialect.

AAVE features other than tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronouns will not be introduced in this dissertation as this dissertation is focused on the discussion of the three major AAVE features just mentioned. The reason why tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronouns of AAVE have been chosen as the focus of this dissertation is that a preliminary AAVE data description of ECSR and WCSR has been made and it shows that there might be a difference between ECSR and WCSR in terms of these three AAVE features.

The rest of this chapter will be giving out the literature review of the tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronoun features of AAVE one section at a time.

2.3 Tense & Aspect Marking of AAVE

By contrast with Standard English and many English dialects where tense marking is obligatory on modals or auxiliaries or lexical verbs, in AAVE verbs are morphologically unmarked for tense (Dillard, 1973). Specifically, tense marking in AAVE shows no morphological exponence on verbs since there is no morphologically overt marking tense on verbs; rather, non verbal lexical items can be used to mark tense (e.g., adverbs; Dillard, 1973). In the first case, the verb is not marked for past tense as in (1a) while it could possibly indicate past tense of the action, or not all verbs would be marked with past tense when there is at least one verb in the sentence has been marked with past tense as in (1b; Dillard, 1973). In the second case, non verbal lexical items (e.g. adverbs) may be added to sentence to indicate the tense, which is the word *yesterday* as in (1c; Dillard, 1973) instead of direct tense marking on the verb.

(1) AAVE (Dillard, 1973)

- a. “I feed the cat and wash the dishes and sweep the floor.”
- b. “I fed the cat and wash the dishes and sweep the floor.”
- c. “Yesterday, I feed the cat and wash the dishes and sweep the floor.”

As in (1a), all the verbs in the sentence – *feed*, *wash*, and *sweep*, are presented with present tense marking, which could possibly be interpreted as past tense or present tense in AAVE. As in (1b), out of all the verbs in the sentence, there is only one verb that is marked with past tense, which is *fed*, while the rest verbs of the sentence – *wash* and *sweep*, are presented with present tense marking. The tense of example (1b) is interpreted as past tense in AAVE, since the tense marking on one of the verbs is considered sufficient for the whole sentence (Dillard, 1973). As in (1c), all verbs – *feed*, *wash*, and *sweep*, are presented without tense marking, while non verbal lexical item, such as the adverb *yesterday*, which is added to the beginning of the sentence indicating the time of the action that those verbs denote, i.e., past. However, Dillard (1973) mainly explains the marking of past tense of AAVE, while it does not explain much about present tense and future tense marking of AAVE.

As for future tense marking in AAVE, there are four future indicators in AAVE, which are *I'ma*, *gonna*, *gon*, and *gon'*, and *gonna*, *gon*, and *gon'* can indicate the future without a preceding auxiliary (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011 & Sidnell, 2002). However, the usage of *I'ma*, *gonna*, *gon*, and *gon'* does not limit to AAVE – for example, the usage of *gonna*

with a preceding auxiliary does appear in informal spoken English (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011 & Sidnell, 2002). Examples can be seen below.

- (2) *I'ma* get dressed (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011).
- (3) He *gonna* get got no matter what you or me do (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011).
- (4) He *gon* see you (Sidnell, 2002).

Aspect marking in AAVE is obligatory, in contrast with Standard English and its dialects (e.g. American English, British English, Irish English, etc.), where aspect marking on the verbs is optional in certain contexts (Dillard, 1973). According to Dillard (1973), the aspect marking of AAVE include the usage of *be* + verb (progressive form) to indicate the action as habitual or continuous without changing the grammatical form of *be* as in (5a) and the absence of *be* before verbs in progressive form to indicate the action as discontinuous as in (5b). The negation of the two different aspect markings of AAVE is different as well. In the first case out of the two aspect markings, the word *don't* is put before *be* + verb (progressive form) as in (5c), while the word *ain't* is put before verb (progressive form) in the second case of aspect marking of AAVE as in (5d; Dillard, 1973).

- (5) AAVE (Dillard 1973)
 - a. "He be goin'."
 - b. "He goin'."
 - c. "He don't be goin'."
 - d. "He ain't goin'."

Dillard (1973) only mentions two cases of aspectual marking of AAVE. However, he does mention the auxiliaries of AAVE, part of which overlaps with aspect marking. The literature review of auxiliaries of AAVE will not be a subsection in this dissertation considering its overlapping with tense marking and aspect marking, and it will be reasonably mentioned in tense marking section and aspect marking section.

Done and *been* take crucial roles in tense & aspect marking in AAVE. As it is mentioned before, *been* + verb (past tense form) is used to indicate pre-recent past tense and *done* + verb (original form) is used to indicate recent past tense in AAVE (Fickett, 1972). Besides that, *done* and *been* also function as additional aspect markers when they are placed right after *done* or *been* as the second *done* or *been* - *been* + *done* is used to indicate that the

action is finished a long time ago as in (6a), and *done + been* is used to indicate that an action has been going on for a long time until recently as in (6b; Fickett, 1972).

- (6) AAVE (Fickett 1972)
- a. “He been done work.”
= He has done work a long time ago.
 - b. “He done been work.”
= He has been doing work until recently.

Green (2002) gives a rather detailed discussion of the aspect marking of AAVE. Specifically, two verbal markers of AAVE have been mentioned – *BIN*, which indicates the eventuality of remote past, and *dən*, which indicates the completion of an eventuality (Green, 2002). According to Green (2002), the aspect marking of AAVE includes the following – *be* + verb (progressive form) indicating that an action is habitual as in (7a), *BIN* + verb (progressive form) indicating that a state or habit is remote past as in (7b), *BIN* + verb (past form) indicating that an action is remote past and it is completed as in (7c), *had* + *BIN* + verb (past form) indicating that an action is remote past perfect as in (7d), *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the resultant state of an action as in (7e), *had* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the past perfect resultant state of an action as in (7f), *should*’*a* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the modal resultant state of an action as in (7g), *BIN* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the remote past resultant state of an action as in (7h), *had* + *BIN* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the remote past perfect resultant state of an action as in (7i), *be* + *dən* verb (past form) indicating the habitual resultant state of an action as in (7j), *’a* + *be* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the future resultant state of an action as in (7k), and *might/may* + *be* + *dən* + verb (past form) indicating the modal resultant state of an action as in (7l). The negation of the above is discussed in a later section.

- (7) AAVE (Green, 2002)
- a. “*be* eating”
= “am usually/always eating” or “usually eats”
 - b. “*BIN* eating”
= “have been eating for a long time”
 - c. “*BIN* ate”
= “ate a long time ago”

- d. “*had BIN ate*”
= “had eaten a long time ago”
- e. “*dən ate*”
= “has/have already eaten”
- f. “*had dən ate*”
= “had already eaten”
- g. “*should’a dən ate*”
= “should have already eaten”
- h. “*BIN dən ate*”
= “finished eating a long time ago”
- i. “*had BIN dən ate*”
= “had already eaten a long time ago”
- j. “*be dən ate*”
= “usually have already eaten”
- k. “*’a be dən ate*”
= “will have already eaten”
- l. “*might/may be dən ate*”
= “might have already eaten”

Out of all the aspect marking of AAVE, Green (2002) specifically discusses *be*, *BIN*, and *dən* in terms of their function as aspect markers in AAVE. Green (2002) found that “aspectual *be* occurs verbs, adjectives, nouns, prepositions, adverbs, *dən* and at the end of the sentence” indicating habitual meaning, that “*BIN* occurs before verbs, adjectives, nouns, prepositions, adverbs and *dən*” indicating something in the remote past, and that “*dən* usually occurs preceding verbs ending in -ed” indicating the resultant state of an event. Besides, there are aspectual combinations of *be*, *BIN*, and *dən*, which are *be* + *dən* indicating the habitual resultant state of an event, *be* + *dən* indicating the future resultant state of an event, and *be* + *dən* indicating the modal resultant state of an event, and *BIN* + *dən* indicating the remote past resultant state of an event (Green, 2002).

Wolfram (2004) does not specifically categorize the tense marking and the aspect marking of AAVE when discussing its grammar. Instead, Wolfram (2004) lists the syntactic features of AAVE, which overlaps tense marking with aspect marking in certain cases. According to Wolfram (2004), the syntactic features of AAVE include the following - copula absence, invariant *be*, completive *done*, sequential *be done*, remote *béen*, simple past *had* +

verb, specialized auxiliaries, irregular verbs, and special subject-verb agreement, all of which are briefly explained and presented with examples in the following.

The copula absence for *is* and *are* is considered as one of the most typical features of AAVE as in (8) (Wolfram, 2004), in which copula *be* is missing before the present participle *acting*. Speaking of present participle, some present participles have evolved into new forms, such as *tryng*, which has become *tryna* in AAVE functioning as a semi-auxiliary in the sentence meaning want or desire (Wolfram, 2004 & Lane, 2014). Example can be seen in (9).

- (8) “They acting silly” (Wolfram, 2004).
= They are acting silly.
- (9) “You *tryna* drink a coke?” (Lane, 2014)
= Do you want a coke?

The invariant *be* in AAVE is considered to indicate habitual events (Wolfram, 2004). In AAVE, the invariant *be* is short for *'ll be* as in (10a) and *'d be* as in (10b) etc. which exist in other varieties of English, such as Standard English (Wolfram, 2004). However, there might be a “shift towards intensified stativity, or super-real status, rather than habituality” on the semantic level of the invariant *be*. Other than the invariant *be*, *be* also has different forms in present & past tense, which are *is* & *was* respectively regardless the person and number of its subject (Gordon, 2003). However, when it comes to present tense, verbs can also be marked with suffix *-s* regardless the person and number of its subject (Green, 2002).

- (10) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)
- a. “She *be* here in a minute, *won't* she?”
= She *will be* here in a minute, *won't* she?
- b. “If they get a DVD player, they *be* happy, *wouldn't* they?”
= If they get a DVD player, they *would be* happy, *wouldn't* they?

Done + verb (past form) functions “like a perfect, referring to an action completed in the recent past, but it can also be used to highlight the change of state or intensify an activity” (Wolfram, 2004). See example (11).

- (11) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)
- a. “They *done* used all the good ones.”

= They have used all the good ones recently.

b. “I *done* told you not to mess up.”

= I have just told you not to mess up.

Sequential *be + done* of AAVE is considered to indicate “future perfect” as in (12a), while there is another use of it, which “functions more like a future resultative-conditional, referring to an inevitable consequence of a general condition or a specific activity” as in (12b) (Wolfram, 2004).

(12) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)

a. “My ice cream *be done* melted by the time we get there.”

= My ice cream *will have melted* by the time we get there.

b. “If you love your enemy, they *be done* eat you alive in this society.”

= If you love your enemy, they *will* eat you alive in this society.

Béen + verb (past tense) is considered to indicate an action that “took place in the distant past” as in (13a) and it is sometimes considered “as the deletion of a contracted form of the perfect” as in (13b) (Wolfram, 2004).

(13) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)

a. “I *béen* had it for about three years.”

= I *have been having* it for about three years.

b. “She’s *béen* married.”

= She *has been* married.

Simple past *had + verb (past/ perfect form)* of AAVE is considered to indicate the simple past tense of an action as in (14), which is “equivalent to the use of the simple past in Standard English” (Wolfram, 2004).

(14) “They *had went* outside and then they *had messed up* the yard” (Wolfram, 2004).

= They *went* outside and then they *messed up* the yard.

Wolfram (2004) lists several words that function as auxiliaries in AAVE, which are *come*, *steady*, and *finna*. According to Wolfram (2004), when functioning as auxiliaries, *come*

is used to “indicate a state of indignation”, and *steady* is used to “mark a continuative intensifying activity”, and *finna* is used to “indicate an immediate future or planned event”. In this case, *come* + verb (progressive form) is considered to indicate “a speaker’s annoyance about the action or event” as in (15) and *steady* + verb (progressive form) is considered to indicate “an intensified, persistent activity” as in (16) (Wolfram, 2004). Example of the usage of *finna* can be seen in (17).

(15) “He *come walkin’* in here like he owned the damn place” (Spears, 1982).

= He walked in here like he owned the damn place.

(16) “Ricky Bell be *steady steppin’* in them number nines” (Baugh, 1983).

= Ricky Bell would be stepping in them number nines.

(17) “I’m *finna* go” (Wolfram, 2004).

= I’m about to go very soon.

Another tense marking feature of AAVE that Wolfram (2004) has mentioned is related to one of the question formations of AAVE – non-subject-auxiliary inversion. According to Wolfram (2004), in AAVE, the subject-auxiliary inversion often does not exist in the *wh*- question in AAVE. Example can be seen in (18).

(18) “Where that is?” (Wolfram, 2004)

= Where is that?

2.4 Negation of AAVE

While Dillard (1973) does not discuss the negation of AAVE, Green (2002) discusses two different negations of AAVE: multiple negation constructions and negative inversion. According to Green (2002), multiple negation construction means that negation of a sentence can be expressed through multiple negators in one single sentence, such as *don’t*, *no*, *nothing* etc. As for negative inversion, if an auxiliary or indefinite noun phrase is put at the beginning of a sentence, it would be marked with negation obligatorily (Green, 2002). See example (19).

(19) AAVE (Green, 2002)

a. “Bruce *don’t* want *no* teacher telling him *nothing* about *no* books.”

= Bruce doesn’t want any teacher telling him anything about any books.

b. “Don’t no game last all night long.”

= No game lasts all night long.

(19a) is interpreted as “Bruce doesn’t want any teacher telling him anything about (any) books” (Green, 2002). Negators like *don’t*, *no*, and *nothing* are in the same sentence, but the addition of negators does not change the meaning of the sentence, which is unlike the two negatives make a positive in Standard English, and technically, the number of negators that can be used in a sentence is not limited (Green, 2002). At the same time, the usage of auxiliary *don’t* following subject *Bruce* instead of using *doesn’t* when describing present third person singular is also a common feature in AAVE (Sidnell, 2002). (19b) is interpreted as “no game lasts all night” (Green, 2002). The rules of negative inversion of AAVE is set, which is *negative initial auxiliary + negative indefinite noun*, which is *don’t + no game* in this case (Green, 2002). Labov (1968) “negative inversion is an optional process which gives additional prominence to the negative”.

Howe & Walker (2000) discusses three features of negation in AAVE, which are the usage of *ain’t*, negative concord, negative proposing and negative inversion. According to them, *ain’t* is used to indicate negation in AAVE in replacement of *be + not* as in (20), *do + not* as in (21), and *have + not* as in (22), which are used in other varieties of English as negative indicators.

(20) “But the boys *ain’t* like the boys is now” (Howe & Walker, 2000).

= But the boys are not like what the boys are now.

(21) “Well, he didn’t do nothin’ much, and I *ain’t* neither” (Labov, 1968).

= Well, he didn’t do anything much, and I didn’t neither.

(22) “What do you expect, you *ain’t* been round here, have you?” (Cheshire, 1982)

= What do you expect, you have not been round here, have you?

Negative concord refers to the negation of all negatable forms in a sentence, including the indefinites and verbs in the sentence (Howe & Walker, 2000). See example (23). At the same time, in (23b), the usage of *got* can be seen as missing auxiliary, which is a usage in but not limited to AAVE (Krug, 2000). Similar usage like *got* in AAVE also include *gots* and *gotta* (Krug, 2000).

(23) AAVE (Howe & Walker, 2000)

- a. "I didn't had no chance to go to no school."
= I didn't have any chance to go to any school.
- b. "No stranger ain't got to come."
= No stranger has got to come.
- c. "Well isn't nobody wouldn't go out."
= Well nobody would go out.

Negative postposing refers to the omission of preverbal negation if there are any negative words in the verb phrase (Howe & Walker, 2000). Examples of the omission of preverbal negation is presented as in (24a), and that of preverbal negation together with negative words in the verb phrase is presented as in (24b).

- (24) AAVE (Howe & Walker, 2000)
- a. "I have nowhere to go."
b. "I don't have anywhere to go."

As for negative inversion, Howe & Walker (2000) does not give detailed illustration on it while only several examples of negative inversion are included as in (25).

- (25) "Can't no one get there" (Howe & Walker, 2000).
= No one can get there.

Wolfram (2004) mainly discusses two typical negation features of AAVE, which are negation concord and several negators that have different usage in AAVE from other varieties of English. He does not give a detailed discussion of each case in AAVE negation. Instead, he briefly considers the two negation features comparing them with different English dialects. For instance, he points out that "AAVE is unlike most European American vernacular varieties in generalizing the use of *ain't* for didn't as well" (Wolfram, 2004). Moreover, he notices that negative concord is a single negative proposition that is "marked both within the verb phrase and on postverbal indefinites" as in (26a), and one type of negative concord that involves AAVE has the form of preverbal indefinite + verbal negative as in (26b). Negative inversion of AAVE is also mentioned in Wolfram (2004) briefly, where it is compared to the preverbal negative pattern and it is considered to have the form of negative auxiliary + indefinite subject as in (26c). Following negative concord, cross-clausal

negative concord is also briefly introduced with examples as in (26d). As for negative indicators, “AAVE uses *ain’t* as a general preverbal negative for present tense *be* (*am not*, *isn’t*, *aren’t*) and for the perfect auxiliary *haven’t/ hasn’t*” and “the generalized past tense variant *wont* for *wasn’t* and *weren’t*”, and other than that, “*ain’t* and *don’t* may be used with but to indicate ‘only’ or ‘no more than’” (Wolfram, 2004). Examples of negative indicators discussed in Wolfram (2004) are presented in (26e-26g).

(26) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)

- a. “They didn’t do nothing about nobody having no money or nothing like that.”
= They didn’t do anything about anybody having any money or anything like that.
- b. “Nobody don’t like him.”
= Nobody likes him.
- c. “Don’t nobody like him.”
= Nobody like him.
- d. “It ain’t no cat can’t get in no coop.”
= There is no cat that can get in a coop.
- e. “She ain’t been there lately.”
= She has not been there lately.
- f. “I ain’t there yesterday.”
= I was not there yesterday.
- g. “She ain’t but three years old.”
= She is no more than three years old.

2.5 Pronouns of AAVE

According to Dillard (1973), the pronoun system does not differentiate between masculine and feminine in some AAVE as in (27a) where pronoun *he* is used to indicate girl, and pronouns in accusative case might be used as possessives before nouns as in (27b) or as nominative to serve as the sentence subject as in (27c).

(27) AAVE (Dillard, 1973)

- a. “*He* a nice little girl.”
= She is a nice little girl.
- b. “*me* book”
= my book

c. “*Me* help you.”

= I help you.

Green (2002) briefly discusses two different expressions of pronouns used in AAVE that is different from Standard English, which are the usage of *theyself* (*theyelves*) as in (28a), and the usage of *-own-* inserted “between the two parts of a reflexive pronoun” meaning self and functioning as “an intensifier that expresses the independence of someone or reinforces the individuality of a person in taking responsibility for an action”, such as *herownself*, *hisownself*, *myownself*, and *theyownselves* as in (28b-28d).

(28) AAVE (Green, 2002)

a. “Them boys call *theyselves* playing basketball.”

= Them boys call *themselves* playing basketball.

b. “She don’t know what’s wrong with *herownself*.”

= She doesn’t know what’s wrong with *herself*.

c. “He cooked his food *hisownself*.”

= He cooked his food *on his own*.

d. “I don’t need any help; I can do it *myownself*.”

= I don’t need any help; I can do it *on my own*.

e. “Let them clean it *theyownselves*.”

= Let them clean it *on their own*.

Wolfram (2004) discusses the pronouns of AAVE in a more detailed manner. *Y’all* is recorded in Wolfram (2004), saying that *y’all*, which indicates second person plural *you*, is a common feature in Southern and Northern AAVE. Example can be seen in (29a). According to Wolfram (2004), AAVE pronouns include the usage of possessive pronouns as in (29b), the usage of *mines* instead of *mine* as in (29c), the usage of *hissself* as in (29d), and “the extension of the objective form *them* for attributive demonstratives” as in (29e). The usage of *’em* is also discussed in Wolfram (2004), which is considered an associative plural in AAVE. Example can be seen in (29f).

(29) AAVE (Wolfram, 2004)

a. “*Y’all* is home”

= *You all* are home.

- b. "It's *they* book."
= It's *their* book.
- c. "The book is *mines*."
= The book is *mine*.
- d. "He washed *hissself*."
= He washed *himself*.
- e. "She likes *them* apples."
- f. "Jerome an '*em*'"
= Jerome and *them*

3. Methodology

In general, I read the relevant literature review on AAVE, chose a number of lyrics from East and West and checked if the features of AAVE were there. Then I created a database of East and West and I compared the two.

This dissertation is aimed to find the morpho-syntactic and lexical similarities and differences between ECSR AAVE and WCSR AAVE. The morpho-syntactic and lexical features of AAVE are too broad to be discussed in details in this dissertation. To narrow down the range of the topics, preliminary data analysis has been conducted. Song *Big Poppa* by The Notorious B.I.G., which is a representative ECSR song, and song *California Love* by 2Pac, which is a representative WCSR song, are selected to conduct the preliminary data analysis. The two songs just mentioned are selected based on the fact that The Notorious B.I.G. and 2Pac are representative rappers of ECSR and WCSR respectively, and both of them were active musically around roughly the same years, i.e. The Notorious B.I.G. 1992-1997, and 2Pac 1990-1996, and both songs were released in 1995. To conduct the preliminary data analysis, the data of the two songs, which is the lyrics, has been taken from a public song lyrics and musical knowledge website called *Genius* (<https://genius.com/>). Every morph-syntactic and lexical feature of AAVE in the two songs has been identified, recorded, and categorized. At the same time, the feature that has been found in the data is calculated its percentage. The steps stated above have led to the observation that copula absence, *be* + verb (progressive form), uninflected verbs, and various expressions of personal pronouns can be found in both songs; but at the same time, morpho-syntactic and lexical features of AAVE other than the ones stated above have been a lot more diversified and spread out in song *Big Poppa* than song *California Love*. Based on the observation made from the preliminary data analysis, prediction has been made that there might be similarities and differences on tense &

aspect marking, negation, and pronoun forms between ECSR AAVE and WCSR AAVE, which is the research question of this dissertation.

To find out the similarities and differences on tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronoun forms of AAVE between ECSR and WCSR, first of all, databases of ECSR & WCSR need to be built. Table 1 and Table 2 in the following show how and why the database of ECSR & WCSR database is formed that way.

Table 1

Database of ECSR

Artist	Album	Song	Year
Wu-Tang Clan	<i>Enter the Wu-Tang (36 Chambers)</i>	<i>Bring Da Rucks</i>	1993
		<i>Shame On A Nigga</i>	
		<i>Clan in Da Front</i>	
		<i>Wu-Tang: 7th Chamber</i>	
		<i>Can It Be All So Simple / Intermission</i>	
The Notorious B.I.G.	<i>Ready to Die</i>	<i>Things Done Changed</i>	1994
		<i>Gimme the Loot</i>	
		<i>Machine Gun Funk</i>	
		<i>Warning</i>	
		<i>Ready To Die</i>	

Table 1 shows the database of ECSR. To build the database of ECSR, two albums have been selected, which are *Enter the Wu-Tang (36 Chambers)* by Wu-Tang Clan, *Ready to Die* by The Notorious B.I.G. The two albums are selected based on the fact that both singers are representative ECSR artists and both albums were released around 1993-1994. As for each album, five songs are selected to build to database as presented in the table. Not every song on the album is selected due to the limited amount of time for this dissertation.

Table 2

Database of WCSR

Artist	Album	Song	Year
Dr. Dre	<i>The Chronic</i>	<i>Fuck wit Dre Day (And Everybody's Celebratin')</i>	1992

		<i>Let Me Ride</i>	
		<i>The Day the Niggaz Took Over</i>	
		<i>Nuthin' But a "G" Thang</i>	
		<i>Deeez Nuuuts</i>	
Snoop Dogg	<i>Doggystyle</i>	<i>G Funk Intro</i>	1993
		<i>Gin and Juice</i>	
		<i>Tha Shiznit</i>	
		<i>Lodi Dodi</i>	
		<i>Murder Was the Case (Death After Visualizing Eternity)</i>	

Table 2 shows the database of WCSR. To build the database of WCSR, two albums have been selected, which are *The Chronic* by Dr. Dre, and *Doggystyle* by Snoop Dogg. The two albums are selected based on the fact that both singers are representative WCSR artists and both albums were released around 1992-1993. As for each album, five songs are selected to build to database as presented in the table. Not every song on the album is selected due to the limited amount of time for this dissertation.

Just like the preliminary data analysis, the data is also taken from the public song lyrics and musical knowledge website called *Genius* (<https://genius.com/>). To build the corpus, extra information other than actual lyrics are excluded from the corpus. In this way, a corpus of total 14,563 words has been built for this dissertation.

As for methodological approaches, both qualitative method and descriptive quantitative method have been applied to this dissertation. The qualitative method, which is also the main approach, means that I was the only participant in the process of identifying and analyzing all the AAVE sub-features that fall under tense and aspect marking, negation, and pronoun. After the databases were created, the data was read through first, and if the data was spotted as having AAVE sub-features that have been recorded in the literature review before, it would be taken, recorded, and categorized. The key of this step is to spot the data that share the same syntactic or lexical sub-feature in a more detailed manner. There are several other techniques - first of all, Excel spreadsheets are used in the second step to build the database. However, when it comes to the actual data, sometimes more than one AAVE feature would be encoded onto one sentence, or one phase, or even one word. In this case, the

data is recorded separately and repeatedly for the purpose of having a clear reference when calculating percentage of each AAVE feature later.

As for the descriptive quantitative method, the AAVE sub-features that fall under tense and aspect marking, negation, and pronoun are calculated their percentage to gain a better understanding of how the AAVE sub-features are applied in ECSR and WCSR, including their similarities and differences.

However, there are limitations. First off, the database could have been a lot bigger to a point that it is valid and solid enough to represent ECSR and WCSR. But due to the limited amount of time that is available for writing the dissertation, the database has been limited to a corpus of 14,563 words. If there is any future study that would focus on this topic, the database definitely can be expanded. Second, the data of this dissertation has been limited to three major aspects, which are tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronouns. Other aspects of AAVE have not been recorded or analyzed in this dissertation. Third, I was the only participant in the process of creating the databases. If there is any future study that would focus on this topic, informants with various linguistic backgrounds could be brought into the data analysis.

4. ECSR: Data

Chapter 4 and chapter 5 of this dissertation will be giving descriptive analysis of the AAVE data found in ECSR and WCSR respectively. The AAVE features that this dissertation is looking for in ECSR database and WCSR database are categorized into three major features, which are: (i) tense & aspect marking, (ii) negation, and (iii) pronouns. To summarize the AAVE features found in the ECSR & WCSR database, Table 3 presents the sub-features of AAVE under three major features – tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronoun.

Table 3

AAVE Features Found in the ECSR & WCSR Database

Tense & Aspect Marking	Negation	Pronouns
Uninflected Verbs	The Usage of Negative Indicator <i>Ain't</i>	The Usage of <i>Y'all</i>
Person & Number Marking on <i>Be (Is & Was)</i>	Double Negation	The Usage of <i>Mines</i>

Person & Number Marking on Suffix -S	The Usage of Auxiliary <i>Don't</i>	The Usage of ' <i>Em</i>
Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation		
Copula / Auxiliary Absence		
<i>Done</i> + Verb (Past Tense Form)		
The Usage of <i>Got, Gots, and Gotta</i>		
The Usage of <i>I'ma, Gonna, Finna, Gon,</i> and <i>Gon'</i> to indicate future		
The Usage of <i>Tryna</i> as a Semi-Auxiliary		

Table 3 shows the sub-features of AAVE under three major features – tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronoun, that are found in the ECSR & WCSR database.

The following three tables show the number and ratio of the AAVE features found in the ECSR database. Table 4 is for tense & aspect marking features. Table 5 is for negation features. Table 6 is for pronoun features. Detailed descriptive analysis of every sub-feature will be presented in the sub-section of chapter 4.

Table 4

AAVE Features in the ECSR Database – Tense & Aspect Marking

Features	Number	Ratio
Uninflected Verbs - <i>Be</i>	8	2.84%
Uninflected Verbs – Other than <i>be</i>	29	10.28%
Person & Number Marking on <i>Be – Is & Was</i>	10	3.55%
Person & Number Marking in the Present Tense – With Suffix -S	1	0.35%
Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation	7	2.48%
Copula / Auxiliary Absence	113	40.07%
<i>Done</i> + Verb (Past Tense Form)	18	6.38%
The Usage of <i>Got, Gots, and Gotta</i>	53	18.79%
The Usage of <i>I'ma, Gonna, Gon,</i> and <i>Gon'</i> to indicate future	9	3.19%

Table 4 shows the tense & aspect marking features of AAVE that are found in the ECSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all the instances found in the ECSR database. As it is shown in the table, the usage of *finna* to indicate future and the usage of *tryna* as a semi-auxiliary is not found in the ECSR database, while both of the sub-features are present in the WCSR database. At the same time, the usage of *gon* to indicate future is only present in the ECSR database instead of the WCSR database. As for number and ratio, it is surprising that the copula / auxiliary absence has been found 113 times in the ECSR database, taking up about 40.07% of the instances, which has become the most often used AAVE feature in the ECSR database. Following the copula / auxiliary absence, the usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta* has showed up 53 times taking up 18.79% and the uninflected verb (other than *be*) has showed up 29 times taking up 10.28%. Other than the three sub-features mentioned above, the rest of the sub-features have an arguably even distribution, taking up from 2.84 % to 6.38%, except for the one and only instance of person & number marking in the present tense - with suffix *-s*.

Table 5

AAVE Features in the ECSR Database – Negation

Features	Number	Ratio
The Usage of Negative Indicator <i>Ain't</i>	18	6.38%
Double Negation	4	1.42%
The Usage of Auxiliary <i>Don't</i>	2	0.71%

Table 5 shows the negation features of AAVE that are found in the ECSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all the instances found in the ECSR database. As it is shown in the table, all three sub-features of negation have been found in the ECSR database. The usage of negative indicator *ain't* has been the most often used negation – 18 instances have been found taking up 6.38%, while double negation showed up 4 times taking up 1.42% and the usage of auxiliary *don't* shown up twice taking up 0.71%.

Table 6

AAVE Features in the ECSR Database – Pronouns

Features	Number	Ratio
The Usage of <i>Y'all</i>	2	0.71%

The Usage of <i>Mines</i>	8	2.84%
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Table 6 shows the pronouns features of AAVE that are found in the ECSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all the instances found in the ECSR database. As it is shown in the table, the usage of *'em* is not present in the ECSR database, while it is present in the WCSR database. At the same time, the usage of *mines* is only present in the ECSR database instead of the WCSR database. As for number and ratio, the usage of *y'all* showed up twice taking up 0.71% and the usage of *mines* showed up 8 times taking up 2.84%.

4.1 Tense & Aspect Marking in ECSR

4.1.1 Uninflected Verbs - *Be*

Verbs in AAVE can remain uninflected, which can be categorized into two different sub-features – the invariant *be* (Wolfram, 2004) and verbs (other than *be*) that stay uninflected and do not agree with subject in terms of person or number (Gordon, 2003), both of which will be discussed in this section.

There are 8 instances of the uninflected *be* in the ECSR database, and the data found can be categorized into three different sub-features - *be* + verb (progressive form) as in example (30), *be* + prepositional phrase as in example (31), and *be* + noun phrase as in example (32).

(30) Crews *be actin'* like they gangs (Smith, Woods, & Jones, 1993, track 2)

(31) *Be* on you like a house on fire (Smith, Woods, & Jones, 1993, track 2)

(32) The damage, my clan understand it, *be* flavor (Smith, Woods, & Jones, 1993, track 2)

In example (30), *be actin'* suggests one of the typical tense marking of AAVE – *be* + verb (progressive form) to indicate that an action is habitual (Green, 2002; Wolfram, 2004). In this case, *be actin'* means are usually or always acting, or usually acts. In example (31) and (32), invariant *be* also functions as indicating habitual events, but with the structure of preceding prepositional phrase *on you* and noun phrase *flavor*.

4.1.2 Uninflected Verbs - *Other than Be*

There are 29 instances found in ECSR AAVE data in which the verb does not agree with the subject in terms of person and number as the examples suggest below -

(33) Ghostface *catch* the blast of a hype verse. My Glock burst, leave in a hearse, I did worse. I come rough, tough like an elephant tusk (Diggs, Grice, Hunter, Woods, & Coles, 1993, track 1)

In example (33) in which the subject *Ghostface* is a third person singular, the verb *catch* is unmarked for person, namely it does not agree with the subject. There might be more than one interpretation on the tense of the action, which is related to the context. If the action belongs to the past, the verb *catch* is supposed to be in past tense form as in *caught* to mark the tense. If the action belongs to the present, the verb *catch* is supposed to be marked with suffix *-es* to indicate the third person singular of the subject *Ghostface*. Neither is the case in this example. If only present tense is discussed in this section, since the interpretation of the context is not certain, the verb does not agree with the subject in terms of person and number, which matches one of the typical features of AAVE (Gordon, 2003).

4.1.3 Person & Number Marking on Be - Is & Was

Other than the uninflected *be*, *be* also shows other forms in the present tense and in the past tense, which are *is* and *was* respectively, in AAVE (Gordon, 2003). This feature has also been found in the ECSR AAVE data in which the usage of *is* in present plural and the usage of *was* in the past tense have appeared 10 times all together, as in example (34) and (35) below.

(34) The glorious days *is* gone (Diggs, Coles, & Woods, 1993, track 5)

(35) Shooting skelly, motherfuckers *was* all friendly (Scott, Owen, & Wallace, 1994, track 4)

In example (34), the subject *the glorious days* is a plural noun phrase, and the verb *is*, which follows *the glorious days*, is in present singular form, which does not agree with the subject in terms of number. However, it is considered as a typical AAVE feature that there is only one form of verb *be* in present plural – *is* (Gordon, 2003). And when it comes to past tense, there is one form of verb *be* – *was* (Gordon, 2003), which is the case in example (35) in which subject *motherfuckers* is in plural form while *was* follows the subject.

4.1.4 Person & Number Marking in the Present Tense – With Suffix -S

Out of all the data of ECSR, there is only one example in which the verb, which is marked with -s, does not agree with the subject in terms of person, as in the following example.

(36) Champion gear that I rock, you get your boots knocked. Then attack you like a pit, then lock shit down. As I come and *freaks* the sound. Hardcore, but givin' you more and more like "Ding!" (Jones et al. 1993, track 4)

In the example presented above, there are two verbs that follow the subject *I*, which are *come* and *freaks* and both verbs are coordinate verbs in this instance. The first verb *come*, which is uninflected, suggests the action is in present tense and agrees with the subject *I* in terms of person. However, the second verb *freaks*, which is marked with suffix -s and indicates third person singular in the present tense, does not agree with the subject *I*, which is first person singular, in terms of person. According to Green (2002) and Trotta & Blyahher (2011), some verbs in AAVE might be marked with suffix -s for various purposes, including functioning as a narrative present marker, which is the case in this example.

4.1.5 Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation

One of the question formations in AAVE is called “non-subject-auxiliary inversion” (Wolfram, 2004), and it is also found in the ECSR AAVE. There are 7 instances in my ECSR database, which show non-subject-auxiliary inversion (37).

(37) So why the fuck he keep looking (Brown et al. 1994, track 3)

In example (37), which is a *wh*- question, the sequence of the sentence still remains subject *he* + verb *keep* instead of having a subject-auxiliary inversion. However, an alternative approach to this sentence would be seeing it as having an absence of auxiliary in question formation. In this way, there is absence of auxiliary, which could be *did* indicating past tense or *does* indicating present tense that could have been placed before subject *he*.

4.1.6 Copula / Auxiliary Absence

Copula / auxiliary absence has been considered as one of the most typical features of AAVE (Wolfram, 2004), which also appears the most in the ECSR AAVE data – the copula / auxiliary absence has appeared 113 times in total. In example (38), there is a lack of copula

between subject *my clan* and the verb *rollin'*, which is in progressive form. In example (39), there is a lack of copula between subject *they* and adjective *fake*. Another approach to example (39) would be seeing the absence of *be* before verbs in progressive form as indicating discontinuous action (Dillard, 1973), which is one of the aspect marking of AAVE.

(38) my clan rollin' like forty macks (Diggs, Grice, Hunter, Woods, & Coles, 1993, track 1)

(39) Yeah, they fake and all that (Diggs, Grice, Hunter, Woods, & Coles, 1993, track 1)

4.1.7 *Done + Verb (Past Tense Form)*

Done + verb (past tense form) has been one of the aspect marking in AAVE indicating that “an action completed in the recent past” or “to highlight the change of state or intensify an activity” (Wolfram, 2004). In the ECSR data, 18 instances in which *done + verb (past tense form)* have been applied to are found as in example (40). In example (40), *done changed* has been applied to indicate that things recently have changed.

(40) Things done changed on this side (Scott, Owen, & Wallace, 1994, track 4)

4.1.8 *Usage of Got, Gots, and Gotta*

According to Trotta & Blyahher (2011), *got* has been applied but not limited to AAVE to replace *have* or *have got* to indicate possession or ownership; and *gotta* is used to replace *have to* or *have got to* indicating obligation. It could be either interpreted as missing auxiliary *have*, which could function as an aspect marker, or interpreted as functioning as a modal auxiliary itself (Krug, 2000). In ECSR AAVE data, *got*, *gots*, and *gotta* all together have appeared 53 times, as in example (41), (42), (43), and (44).

(41) Yo, let's go do what we *got* (Jones, 1993, track 4)

(42) you ain't *got* to explain shit (Brown et al. 1994, track 3)

(43) I *gots* to make the fabrics (Jones, 1993, track 4)

(44) caps I *gotta* peel some (Harvey & Wallace, 1994, track 4)

In example (41), *got* indicates ownership and it alternatively could be interpreted as *let's go do what we have* or *let's go do what we have got*. In example (42), (43), and (44), *got to*, *gots to*, and *gotta* indicate obligation, and alternative interpretation would be – *you don't*

have got to explain shit, I have got to make the fabrics, and caps I have got to peel some. As for *gots*, it fits one of the AAVE features that some verbs might be marked with suffix *-s* as a narrative marker and shares similarity to the usage of *got* or *gotta* (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011).

4.1.9 Usage of *I'ma*, *Gonna*, *Gon*, and *Gon'* to Indicate Future

In ECSR AAVE, future indicator *gonna* & *I'ma* (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011), and *gon* & *gon'* (Sidnell, 2002) have been found. However, other than the usage of *I'ma*, not every instance that includes *gonna*, *gon*, or *gon'* has been recorded – only instances that lack a preceding copula or auxiliary have been recorded since the “*gonna* with a preceding auxiliary be is an unexceptional and prevalent feature of informal spoken English” (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011). Therefore, a total of 9 instances that include the usage of *gonna*, *gon*, and *gon'* without a preceding auxiliary or copula have been found in ECSR AAVE, and 2 instances with the usage of *I'ma* have been recorded. Examples are presented as in (45), (46), (47), and (48).

- (45) We *gon'* keep goin' (Diggs, Coles, & Woods, 1993, track 5)
- (46) Now we *gonna* drink some good Night train (Jones, 1993, track 4)
- (47) Time to go, we *gon* put you out your misery motherfucker (Wallace, Combs, Harvey, & Mason, 1994, track 6)
- (48) *I'ma* start from the top (Diggs, Coles, & Woods, 1993, track 5)

As in example (45), (46), and (47), *gon'*, *gonna*, and *gon* directly follow subject *we* without any copula in between and indicate future as a derivation of *going + to* (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011). Thus, alternative interpretations of example (45), (46), and (47) could be – *we are going to keep going*; *now we are going to drink some good Night train*; and *we are going to put you out your misery motherfucker*. The *I'ma* as in example (48) is considered as “an explicit marker of the 1per. sg.” (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011).

4.2 Negation of ECSR AAVE

4.2.1 Usage of Negative Indicator *Ain't*

Ain't is used as a negative indicator as a replacement of “*have + not*, *be + not*, and *do + not*, in both present and past temporal contexts” (Howe, 2005). However, in the ECSR data, instances that include the usage of negative indicator *ain't* have been categorized based on its following environment instead of on whether it is the replacement of *have + not*, *be + not*, or *do not*, for the purpose of avoiding alternative and different interpretations of its contexts and

thus its tense and aspect. In this way, the usage of *ain't* found in ECSR AAVE has been categorized into *ain't* + verb (progressive form), *ain't* + verb (past tense form), *ain't* + *gonna*, *ain't* + noun phrase, *ain't* + clause, and *ain't* + prepositional phrase, which make up to 18 instances in total. Examples are presented as in (49) – (54).

- (49) I *ain't wettin'* fame (Diggs, Grice, Hunter, Woods, & Coles, 1993, track 1)
- (50) But *ain't heard* half of it yet (Smith, Woods, & Jones, 1993, track 2)
- (51) They *ain't gonna* roll up (Brown et al. 1994, track 3)
- (52) And it *ain't a dream* (David, Bacharach, Harvey, & Wallace, 1994, track 5)
- (53) *Ain't a damn thing* changed (Jones, 1993, track 4)
- (54) this *ain't back in the days* (Scott, Owen, & Wallace, 1994, track 4)

4.2.2 Double Negation

Negative concord, which refers to the negation of all negatable forms in a sentence (Howe & Walker, 2000), has also been found in ECSR AAVE. However, only double negation, which belongs to negative concord, has been found. There are four instances in total as in example (55).

- (55) I *don't* wanna see *no* crying at my funeral (Wallace, Combs, Harvey, & Mason, 1994, track 6)

In example (55), there are two words that have been marked with negation, which are auxiliary *don't* and *no* preceding object *crying*. An alternative interpretation to this example is that *I don't wanna see any crying at my funeral*.

4.2.3 Usage of Auxiliary Don't

According to Sidnell (2002), the usage of *don't* instead of *doesn't* when describing present third person singular is more of a general pattern in AAVE, which is also found in ECSR AAVE with two instances, as in (56).

- (56) that *don't* got nothin' to do with my shit (Jones, 1993, track 4)

In example (56), *don't* is used to indicate negation instead of *doesn't*, even though the subject *that* is a third person singular and the context indicates present tense.

4.3 Pronoun Forms of ECSR AAVE

4.3.1 Usage of *Y'all*

Y'all, which is used to indicate second person plural, has been considered as a common usage in Southern and Northern AAVE (Wolfram, 2004). Two instances have been found in ECSR AAVE as in example (57) in which *y'all* is applied to indicate you in second person plural, which can also be interpreted through its coordinate noun phrase *motherfuckers* as it is ended with suffix *-s* indicating plural.

(57) And *y'all* motherfuckers come with me if you want to (Wallace, Combs, Harvey, & Mason, 1994, track 6)

4.3.2 Usage of *Mines*

The usage of *mines* instead of *mine* is quite often in AAVE, especially in younger speakers (Wolfram, 2004). There are 8 instances of *mines* in the ECSR database, although the usage of *mine* applied as well as in example (58).

(58) What's *mines* is *mines* and what's yours is *mine* (Brown et al. 1994, track 3)

5. WCSR: Data

The following three tables show the number and ratio of the AAVE features found in the WCSR database. Table 7 is for tense & aspect marking features. Table 8 is for negation features. Table 9 is for pronoun features. Detailed descriptive analysis of every sub-feature will be presented in the sub-section of chapter 5.

Table 7

AAVE Features in the WCSR Database – Tense & Aspect Marking

Features	Number	Ratio
Uninflected Verbs - <i>Be</i>	6	3.11%
Uninflected Verbs – Other than <i>be</i>	4	2.07%
Person & Number Marking on <i>Be – Is & Was</i>	2	1.04%
Person & Number Marking in the Present Tense – With Suffix <i>-S</i>	9	4.66%
Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation	6	3.11%
Copula / Auxiliary Absence	33	17.10%

<i>Done + Verb (Past Tense Form)</i>	1	0.52%
The Usage of <i>Got, Gots, and Gotta</i>	53	27.46%
The Usage of <i>I'ma, Gonna, Finna, and Gon'</i> to indicate future	15	7.77%
The Usage of <i>Tryna</i> as a Semi-Auxiliary	1	0.52%

Table 7 shows the tense & aspect marking features of AAVE that are found in the WCSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all instances found in the WCSR database. As it is shown in the table, the usage of *gon* to indicate future is not present in the WCSR database, while the usage of *finna* to indicate future and the usage of *tryna* as a semi-auxiliary are only present in the WCSR database instead of the ECSR database. As for number and ratio, the usage of *got, gots, and gotta* to indicate future has become the most often used feature – there are 53 instances in total taking up 27.46%, which is followed by copula / auxiliary absence, which has showed up 33 times taking up 17.10%. The rest of the features have shown arguably even distributions, ranging from 1.04% to 7.77%, except for the usage of *done + verb (past tense form)* and the usage of *tryna* as a semi-auxiliary, both of which have only showed up once in the WCSR database.

Table 8

AAVE Features in the WCSR Database - Negation

Features	Number	Ratio
The Usage of Negative Indicator <i>Ain't</i>	22	11.40%
Double Negation	6	3.11%
The Usage of Auxiliary <i>Don't</i>	6	3.11%

Table 8 shows the negation features of AAVE that are found in the WCSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all the instances found in the WCSR database. All the three sub-features of negation in AAVE have been found in the WCSR database, of which the usage of negative indicator *ain't* has become the most used feature – it showed up 22 times taking up 11.40%. Both double negation and the usage of auxiliary *don't* have showed up 6 times, taking up 3.11% respectively.

Table 9*AAVE Features in the WCSR Database – Pronouns*

Features	Number	Ratio
The Usage of <i>Y'all</i>	4	2.07%
The Usage of <i>'Em</i>	25	12.95%

Table 9 shows the pronoun features of AAVE that are found in the WCSR database, its relative number of instances, and the ratio that it takes up of all the instances found in the WCSR database. As it is shown in the table, the usage of *mines* is not present in the WCSR database, while the usage of *'em* is only present in the WCSR database instead of the ECSR database. As for number and ratio, the usage of *'em* is used a lot more often than the usage *y'all* – there are 25 instances of *'em* taking up 12.95%, while there are 4 instances of *y'all* taking up 2.07%.

5.1 Tense & Aspect Marking of WCSR AAVE**5.1.1 Uninflected Verbs - Be**

The usage of uninflected *be* show up 6 times in the WCSR AAVE data, which includes the structure of *be* + verb (progressive form) as in example (59) and *be* + noun phrase as in (60). In example (59) and (60), the uninflected *be* is applied as in *be goin'* and *be me* to indicate that the action or the event is habitual (Green, 2002; Wolfram, 2004).

(59) 'Cause they know about the shit that we *be goin'* through (Ruffin, Young, & Broadus, 1993, track 5)

(60) You can't see the D-O-double-G, 'cause that *be me* (Ruffin, Young, & Broadus, 1993, track 5)

5.1.2 Uninflected Verbs – Other than Be

Some verbs in AAVE might be uninflected and do not agree with the subject in terms of person and number in present tense (Gordon, 2003). This feature is different from the feature as in 5.1.1 since the feature 5.1.1 emphasizes the verbs that are marked with suffix *-s* and function as a narrative marker. Four instances have been recorded in WCSR AAVE data as in example (61) in which the verb *drop* is uninflected and its subject *another motherfucker* is a singular.

(61) another motherfucker *drop* (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

5.1.3 Person & Number Marking on Be – Is & Was

The feature that verb *be* only has form *is* in plural present and form *was* in past tense (Gordon, 2003) has only been found once respectively in WCSR AAVE as example (62) and (63). In example (62), the verb *be* is presented as *is*, which is present singular, while the coordinate subject *Snoop Doggy Dogg and Dr. Dre* are plural. In example (63), the verb *be* is presented *was*, which is past tense singular, while the subject *motherfuckers* is plural.

(62) Snoop Doggy Dogg and Dr. Dre *is* at the door (Patterson, Haywood, Curry, Young, & Broadus, 1992, track 5)

(63) The bitch was strong, the kids *was* gone (Nakamura, Ei, Walters, Fletcher, & Broadus, 1993, track 7)

5.1.4 Person & Number Marking in the Present Tense – With Suffix -S

As for verbs that are marked with suffix *-s* and that do not agree with subject in terms of person and number in present tense, there are 9 times in the WCSR database, as in example (64) and (65).

(64) The sounds of a dog *brings* me to another day (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

(65) How can I *makes* my grip (Ruffin, Young, & Broadus, 1993, track 5)

In example (64) and (65), the verb *brings*, which is marked with suffix *-s*, does not agree with subject *the sounds*, which is in plural form; and the verb *makes*, which is marked with suffix *-s*, does not agree with the subject *I*, which is first person singular. In this case, it is considered as a narrative marker in AAVE (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011).

5.1.5 Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation

The non-auxiliary inversion, which is one of the question formation of AAVE (Wolfram, 2004), has been recorded 6 times in the WCSR data, all of which have been the same to example (66). Example (66) is a *wh-* question in which the sequence of the sentence is subject + verb and there is no auxiliary. Another approach to such example would be seeing the question as a lack of auxiliary, such as *do*.

(66) What you wanna do? (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

5.1.6 Copula / Auxiliary Absence

The copula / auxiliary absence (Wolfram, 2004) has been recorded 33 times in the WCSR AAVE data, as in example (67) in which the structure subject + verb (progressive form) can be seen.

(67) Helicopters flyin', these motherfuckers tryin' (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

5.1.7 Done + Verb (Past Tense Form)

Done + verb (past tense form), which is used to indicate a recent completed action in AAVE aspect marking (Wolfram, 2004), has only been found once in WCSR AAVE data, as in example (68).

(68) The shit *done hit* the fan (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

5.1.8 Usage of Got, Gots, & Gotta

The usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta*, all together, have been recorded 53 times in WCSR AAVE data. Examples are presented as in (69), (70), (71), and (72). In example (69), *got* is used to replace *have* or *have got to* indicating ownership (Trotta & Blyahher, 2011). In example (70), (71), and (72), *got to*, *gots to*, and *gotta*, can be seen as indicating obligation in replacement of *have got to* (Krug, 2000; Trotta & Blyahher, 2011). Thus, auxiliary *have* is missing in these examples.

(69) so I know you *got* your gat (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

(70) Man, I *got to* piss (Allen & Broadus, 1993, track 2)

(71) It's jumping off in Compton so I *gots to* get my loot on (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

(72) *Gotta* get the chronic (Young, Broadus, & Collins, 1992, track 3)

5.1.9 Usage of I'ma, Gonna, Finna, & Gon'

As for future indicators in AAVE, the usage of *I'ma*, *gonna*, *finna*, and *gon'* have been found in WCSR AAVE, which make up to 15 instances in total. However, only the usage of *gonna*

and *gon'* without any auxiliary preceding have been considered in this case. To break down the data, there are 11 instances of *I'ma* as in example (73), 1 instance of *finna* as in example (74), 1 instance of *gonna* as in example (75), and 1 instance of *gon'* as in example (76).

(73) *I'ma* say this (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

(74) I'm *finna* fuck a bitch (Ruffin, Young, & Broadus, 1993, track 5)

(75) we *gonna* creep to South Central (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

(76) So we *gon'* smoke an ounce to this (Dean et al. 1994, track 3)

5.1.10 Usage of *Tryna* as A Semi-Auxiliary

The usage of *tryna* is recorded once in the WCSR AAVE data as in example (77) in which *tryna* functions as a semi-auxiliary indicating want or desire (Lane, 2014). It is considered as the present participle of *try* from urban AAVE (Lane, 2014).

(77) You *tryna* check my homie (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

5.2 Negation of WCSR AAVE

5.2.1 *Ain't*

The usage of negative indicator *ain't* has been found 22 times in the WCSR AAVE data, where *ain't* + verb (progressive form), *ain't* + verb (past tense form), *ain't* + noun phrase, and *ain't* + prepositional phrase have been recorded as in example (78), (79), (80), and (81).

(78) And I *ain't* even *swaggin'* them thangs (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

(79) Everybody got they cups, but they *ain't* *chipped* in (Dean et al. 1994, track 3)

(80) And no, this *ain't* *Aerosmith* (Young, Broadus, & Collins, 1992, track 3)

(81) If you *ain't* *down* for the Africans here in the United States (Curry, Collins, Arnaud, & Broadus, 1992, track 4)

5.2.2 Double Negation

Double negation, which belongs to negative concord, has been found 6 times in the WCSR AAVE data as in example (83) in which both auxiliary *didn't* and subject *nobody* are marked with negation. An alternative interpretation of example (82) would be *nobody wanted to speak*.

(82) *Didn't nobody* wanna speak (Young, Broadus, & Collins, 1992, track 3)

5.2.3 Usage of Auxiliary *Don't*

The usage of auxiliary *don't* has been found 6 times in the WCSR AAVE as in example (83) in which auxiliary *don't* is used to agree with subject *it* instead of auxiliary *doesn't*.

(83) It *don't* stop (Young et al. 1993, track 2)

5.3 Pronoun Forms of WCSR AAVE

5.3.1 Usage of *Y'all*

The usage of *y'all* that indicates second person plural (Wolfram, 2004) has been found 4 instances in the WCSR AAVE as in the example (84).

(84) Are *y'all* done? (Young, Hale, Broadus, Wolfe, & Arnaud, 1992, track 6)

5.3.2 Usage of *'Em*

According to Wolfram (2004), the usage of *'em*, which suggests associative plural, has been found but not limited in English creoles. In WCSR AAVE data, the usage of *'em* has been found 25 times as in example (85), which functions as plural pronoun.

(85) Gotta give *'em* what they want (Patterson, Haywood, Curry, Young, & Broadus, 1992, track 5)

6. Comparing ECSR and WCSR

In general, when looking for the sub-features that fall under the three major features of AAVE – tense & aspect marking, negation, and pronouns, the ECSR database and WCSR database share very similar sub-features. For example, when looking for tense & aspect marking sub-features in both databases, there are 9 sub-features that both ECSR & WCSR databases have in common as listed in Table 8, while there are only 3 sub-features that only exist in one database or the other – the usage of *gon*, *finna*, and *tryna*. Besides the tense & aspect marking sub-features just mentioned, it is surprising to see the amount of other tense & aspect marking sub-features of AAVE that do not exist in neither databases – for example, the usage of *BIN* and *dən*. When looking for negation sub-features of AAVE in both databases, both databases share exactly the same AAVE negation sub-features as listed in

Table 9. When looking for pronoun sub-features of AAVE in both databases, there is 1 sub-feature that both databases have in common, which is the usage of *y'all* as listed in Table 10, while there are 2 sub-features that both databases do not share with each other, which are the usage of *mines* and *'em*. The following three tables present the sub-features that two databases have in common – Table 8 is for tense & aspect marking sub-features, Table 9 is for negation sub-features, and Table 10 is for pronoun sub-features.

Table 8

AAVE Features in ECSR & WCSR Database – Tense & Aspect Marking

Features	Number (ECSR : WCSR)	Ratio (ECSR : WCSR)
Uninflected Verbs - <i>Be</i>	8 : 6	2.84% : 3.11%
Uninflected Verbs – Other than <i>be</i>	29 : 4	10.28% : 2.07%
Person & Number Marking on <i>Be – Is & Was</i>	10 : 2	3.55% : 1.04%
Person & Number Marking in the Present Tense – With Suffix - <i>S</i>	1 : 9	0.35% : 4.66%
Non-Subject-Auxiliary Inversion in Question Formation	7 : 6	2.48% : 3.11%
Copula / Auxiliary Absence	113 : 33	40.07% : 17.10%
<i>Done</i> + Verb (Past Tense Form)	18 : 1	6.38% : 0.52%
The Usage of <i>Got, Gots, and Gotta</i>	53 : 53	18.79% : 27.46%
The Usage of <i>I'ma, Gonna, and Gon'</i> to indicate future	8 : 14	2.84% : 7.25%

Table 8 shows the tense & aspect marking sub-features of AAVE that are found in both ECSR database and WCSR database, the comparison of its number of how many times it shows up in its own database, and the comparison of its ratio of how much it takes up in its own database. Relative data of features, including the usage of *gon* and *finna* to indicate future and the usage of *tryna* as a semi-auxiliary, all of which only show up once in its own database, are not present in this table since they are not the features that both ECSR & WCSR database have in common.

Surprisingly, the usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta* have showed up exactly 53 times in both ECSR & WCSR database. However, because the AAVE instances found in ECSR database is slightly more than the one of WCSR database – 282 versus 193, the percentage that the usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta* takes up in ECSR database is slightly lower than that of WCSR database – 18.79% versus 27.46%. Two features have shown similar frequency of occurrence – the uninflected *be* and the non-subject-auxiliary inversion in question formation, both of which have showed 6-8 times in its own database and take up 2.48%-3.11%. There are four features that show up a lot more in ECSR database than in WCSR database – the uninflected verbs (other than *be*), person & number marking on *be* (*is* & *was*), copula / auxiliary absence, and *done* + verb (past tense form). For example, the copula / auxiliary absence has showed 113 times in the ECSR database taking up 40.07%, while it has only showed up 33 times in the WCSR database taking up 17.10%. Similar cases go to the other three features – the uninflected verbs (other than *be*) show up 29 times in ECSR database taking up 10.28% while it only shows up 4 times in WCSR database taking up 2.07%; person & number marking on *be* (*is* & *was*) shows up 10 times in ECSR database taking up 3.55% while it only shows up twice in WCSR database taking up 1.04%; *done* + verb (past tense form) shows up 18 times on ECSR database taking up 6.28% while it only shows up once in WCSR database taking up 0.52%. There are two features left - person & number marking in the present tense (with suffix *-s*) and the usage of *I'ma*, *gonna*, and *gon'* to indicate future, both of which have showed up a lot more in the WCSR database than in the ECSR database. Person & number marking in the present tense (with suffix *-s*) shows up only once in the ECSR database taking up 0.35% while it shows up 9 times in the WCSR database taking up 4.66%. The usage of *I'ma*, *gonna*, and *gon'* to indicate future shows up 8 times in the ECSR database taking up 2.84% while it shows 14 times in the WCSR database taking up 7.25%.

Table 9

AAVE Features in ECSR & WCSR Database – Negation

Features	Number (ECSR : WCSR)	Ratio (ECSR : WCSR)
The Usage of Negative Indicator <i>Ain't</i>	18 : 22	6.38% : 11:40%
Double Negation	4 : 6	1.42% : 3.11%
The Usage of Auxiliary <i>Don't</i>	2 : 6	0.71% : 3.11%

Table 9 shows the negation features of AAVE that are found in both ECSR database and WCSR database, the comparison of its number of how many times it shows up in its own database, and the comparison of its ratio of how much it takes up in its own database.

In general, the three negation features – the usage of negative indicator *ain't*, double negation, and the usage of auxiliary *don't*, show up slightly more in the WCSR database than in the ECSR database, which is interesting because the AAVE instances found in WCSR database is less than that of ECSR database – 193 : 282. The usage of negative indicator *ain't* shows up 18 times in the ECSR database taking up 6.38%, while it shows up 22 times in the WCSR database taking up 11.40%. Double negation shows up 4 times in the ECSR database taking up 1.42%, while it shows up 6 times in the WCSR database taking up 3.11%. The usage of auxiliary *don't* shows up twice in the ECSR database taking up 0.71%, while it shows up 6 times in the WCSR database taking up 3.11%.

Table 10

AAVE Features in ECSR & WCSR Database – Pronouns

Features	Number (ECSR : WCSR)	Ratio (ECSR : WCSR)
The Usage of <i>Y'all</i>	2 : 4	0.71% : 2.07%

Table 10 shows the pronoun features of AAVE that are found in both ECSR database and WCSR database, the comparison of its number of how many times it shows up in its own database, and the comparison of its ratio of how much it takes up in its own database.

Relative data of features, including the usage of *mines* and the usage of *'em*, are not present in this table since they are not the features that exist in both databases.

The frequency of occurrence of *y'all* does not have much differences between two databases – it shows twice in the ECSR database taking up 0.71% and 4 times in the WCSR database taking up 2.07%.

7. Conclusion

In general, the two databases built for this dissertation share a very similar group of sub-features, which, in a way, means that the two varieties share a very similar group of sub-

features. At the same time, there are also some sub-features that only exist in one database or the other.

As for the tense & aspect marking sub-features, there are some sub-features that showed up extremely similar times in the two databases – the uninflected *be*, the non-subject-auxiliary inversion in question formation, and the usage of *got*, *gots*, and *gotta*, while there are some other sub-features that have shown a huge difference in terms of how many times it showed up in its database, such as the copula absence and the usage of *done* + verb (past tense form). In this way, it could say that the two varieties share some sub-features that have similar frequency of usage, while the two varieties also have some sub-features that differ greatly in terms of frequency. As for the negation sub-features, both databases share the same three sub-features - the usage of negative indicator *ain't* has been the most often used sub-feature in both databases, while the other two sub-features – double negation and the usage of *don't* have shown up a lot less than the usage of *ain't*. Besides, the WCSR database has shown more frequency of the negation sub-features than the ECSR database. In this way, it could say that the two varieties have the same negation features, and the WCSR variety might use negation slightly more than the ECSR variety. As for the pronoun sub-features, the usage of *y'all* has been the only sub-feature that two databases have in common and the WCSR database has more of it than the ECSR database as well. It could only say the usage of *y'all* exists in both varieties, and the WCSR variety might use it more often than the ECSR variety.

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